

Terpenoids—Part LVIII

New Syntheses of Iso-Bisabolene, β -Bisabolene and β -Terpineol

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Employing β -ketosulphoxides and their alkylated derivatives as key intermediates, facile syntheses of title compounds have been achieved.

In continuation of our synthetic studies¹ based upon the easy availability of β -ketosulphoxides² and corresponding alkylated derivatives³ followed by reductive cleavage of methyl sulphoxide^{2,4} group to yield suitable ketones which are subsequently elaborated to the desired compounds through other well-established reactions, we report new syntheses of isobisabolene, β -bisabolene and β -terpineol in the present communication.

Isobisabolene, a monocyclic sesquiterpene hydrocarbon, isolated from vetiver oil derived from *Vetivera zizanioides* Linn⁵, has been assigned to constitution (I) on the basis of spectroscopic studies and chemical evidence. Further support for this structure has been adduced from a recently reported synthesis⁶.

Present investigations describe a clean synthesis of the compound (I) along the following reaction sequence:—

1. O. P. Vig, J. M. Sehgal, M. M. Mahajan and S. D. Sharma, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1969, **46**, 893.
2. E. J. Corey and M. J. Chaykovsky, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, **86**, 1639; 1965, **87**, 1345.
3. P. G. Gassman and G. D. Richmond, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1966, **31**, 2355.
4. G. A. Russel and G. J. Michol, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1966, **88**, 5498.
5. P. S. Kalsi, K. K. Chakravarti and S. C. Bhattacharya, *Tetrahedron*, 1962, **18**, 1165.
6. O. P. Vig, Inder Raj, J. P. Salota and K. L. Matta, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1969, **46**, 205.

The carbonyl group in 4-carbomethoxy-cyclohexanone (II), the starting material, was protected by ketal formation with ethylene glycol. The resulting ketal ester (III) was converted into 1-(1-oxo-2-methyl-sulphinyl-ethyl)-4,4-ethylenedioxy-cyclohexane (IV) by reaction with methyl sulphinyl carbanion². Alkylation of β -keto-sulphoxide (IV) with

isoprene bromide in D.M.F. employing sodium hydride as a base³ and the subsequent reductive cleavage of alkylated product with aluminium amalgam in aqueous T.H.F.² afforded the pure ketal ketone (V) after chromatography over alumina using 1 : 4-benzene petroleum ether (40–60°) mixture as eluent and repeated fractionation of the product. This was submitted to Wittig⁷ reaction with methylene phosphorane to get 6-methyl-2-(4,4-ethylenedioxy-cyclohexyl)-1,5-heptadiene (VI) which was chromatographed over alumina. De-ketalisation of the ketal (VI) with acetone and aqueous hydrochloric acid (10%) at room temperature furnished the ketone (VII). The ketone (VII) was converted into (I) by Wittig reaction⁷ with methylene triphenyl phosphorane. I.R. spectrum of the purified synthetic product showed peaks at 3070, 1775 (overtone), 1640, 1475, 1380, 1105, 992, 890, 833, 815 and 788 cm^{-1} which are in good agreement with those of the natural product and the one synthesised earlier in our laboratory⁶.

β -Bisabolene, another monocyclic sesquiterpene hydrocarbon isomeric with isobisabolene, occurs widely in essential oils—particularly in bergamot oil, carrot oil, lemon oil and rhizome of *Petasites officinalis* Moench⁸. Physical characteristics and chemical studies^{8,9} of this natural product led to the formulation (VIII) which has been corroborated by its earlier syntheses^{10–14}.

In the present studies, a new and facile synthesis of the compound has been achieved through the application of β -ketosulphoxide as shown below :

7. Richard Greenwald, Michael Chaykovsky and E. J. Corey, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1963, **28**, 1128.
8. Simonsen, *The Terpenes*, Vol. 3, Cambridge Univ. Press, 1952, 9.
9. J. Pliva, V. Herout and F. Sorm, *Colln. Trav. Chim. Thecosl.*, 1951, **16**, 158; 1961, **26**, 2552.
10. O. P. Vig, K. L. Matta, Gurdip Singh and Inder Raj, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1966, **43**, 27.
11. Manjarrez and Guzman, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1961, **31**, 3481.
12. O. P. Vig, J. P. Salota, Baldev Vig and Bhagat Ram, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1966, **5**, 475.
13. A. Eschonmoser, J. Schreiber and W. Keller, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1951, **34**, 1667.
14. A. J. Birch and A. R. Murray, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, 1818.

To start with, 1-carbethoxy-4-methyl-3-cyclohexene (IX) was prepared by the inverse Grignard reaction of methyl magnesium iodide on 4-carbethoxy-cyclohexanone and the subsequent dehydration of the reaction product with POCl_3 and pyridine at room temperature¹⁵. The resulting ester was transformed into the ketone (XI) through the formation of β -keto-sulphoxide², alkylation with isoprene bromide³ and the reductive cleavage of the C-S bond².

The ketone (XI) was purified by chromatography over alumina followed by repeated fractionation and its I.R. spectrum was found to be identical with that of a previously prepared sample¹⁰. The pure ketone thus obtained was subjected to Wittig reaction⁷ with methylene triphenylphosphorane to furnish β -bisabolene (VIII) which was chromatographed over neutral alumina and subsequently distilled. Comparison of the I.R. spectrum of (VIII) with that of the natural and previously prepared samples¹⁰⁻¹⁴ clearly established the identity of the synthesised product.

β -Terpineol, a monocyclic monoterpene tertiary alcohol, has been found to occur in nature in the nutmeg oil¹⁶. It has been assigned the constitution (XII) on the basis of physical and chemical data¹⁷. Vig *et al* have synthesised this alcohol earlier through two different routes^{18,19}. However, we report another elegant synthesis employing β -keto-sulphoxide as key intermediate. The reaction scheme proceeds as follows :

β -Ketosulphoxide (IV) was reduced with aluminium amalgam in aqueous T.H.F.² to obtain 4-acetyl-1,1-ethylenedioxy-cyclohexane (XIII). The ketal ketone so formed was chromatographed over alumina [elution with benzene-petroleum ether (40-60°) mixture in the ratio 1 : 4] and further purified by distilling it twice under vacuum. The ketal ketone (XIII) was converted into 4-isopropenyl-cyclohexanone (XV) through two steps involving

15. L. H. Sarett, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, **70**, 1454.

16. Lee, Kauffman, Harten and Liezabitowski, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1963, **58**, 4974d.

17. A. R. Pinder, "The Chemistry of Terpenes", Chapman and Hall Ltd., London, 1960, p. 51.

18. O. P. Vig, K. L. Matta, Gurdeep Singh and Inder Raj, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1965, **42**, 581.

19. O. P. Vig, J. C. Kapoor and S. D. Sharma, *ibid.*, 1968, **45**, 11.

Wittig reaction and deketalisation exactly as described in literature²⁰. The ketone (XV) was confirmed through its I.R. spectrum and the formation of a yellow D.N.P. (m.p. 129–30°). On submission to Grignard reaction with methyl magnesium, iodide, the ketone yielded the carbinol (XII). I.R. spectrum of the synthesised alcohol was superimposable with that of the natural product.

EXPERIMENTAL*

1-Carboethoxy-4,4-ethylenedioxy-cyclohexane (III): A mixture of 4-carboethoxy-cyclohexanone (II, 12 g.), ethylene glycol (5 g.), anhydrous benzene (150 ml.) and *p*-toluene sulphonic acid (50 mg.) was refluxed under a continuous water separator for 6 hrs (120°). The reaction mixture was then cooled, neutralised with saturated sodium bicarbonate solution and worked up in the usual way when 14 g. (93%) of the ketal ester (III) distilled over at 120–22°/7 mm., η_D^{30} 1.4628. (Found: C, 61.82; H, 8.53. $C_{11}H_{18}O_4$ requires C, 61.66; H, 8.47%).

Infrared spectrum showed characteristic peaks at 1745 cm^{-1} (ester); and 1040 cm^{-1} (ketal).

1-(1-Oxo-2-methylsulphinyl-ethyl)-4,4-ethylenedioxy-cyclohexane (IV): To methyl sulphanyl carbanion, prepared from sodium hydride (2.30 g.) and dimethylsulphoxide (48 ml.) under nitrogen atmosphere, was added an equal volume (48 ml.) of dry T.H.F. and the contents cooled in an ice bath. This was followed by the dropwise addition with stirring, of the ketal ester (III). After stirring for 1 hr more at room temperature, the reaction mixture was poured into water (200 ml.), acidified at 0° with hydrochloric acid (12 ml.) and extracted with chloroform. The extract was washed with water, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and evaporated to furnish the β -ketosulphoxide as a semi-solid (yield 7.5 g., 65%) which was used as such for further reactions.

5-Methyl-1-(4,4-ethylenedioxy-cyclohexyl)-4-hexen-1-one (V): Dry dimethyl formamide (45 ml.) was added to sodium hydride (0.395 g.) under an atmosphere of nitrogen. The resulting slurry was cooled, stirred and the solution of β -ketosulphoxide (IV, 4 g.) in dry D.M.F. (15 ml.) added to it slowly so as to keep the ensuing reaction under control. Stirring

20. O. P. Vig, Suresh Chander, (Miss) Jasbir Puri and S. D. Sharma, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1968, 6, 63.

* Melting and boiling points are uncorrected. Microanalysis was done by Mr. B. N. Anand, Panjab University Chemistry Department, Chandigarh. I.R. spectra were recorded on Beckmann IR-5 with sodium chloride optics using thin liquid films.

was continued at room temperature till the evolution of hydrogen had ceased. The reaction mixture was again cooled and isoprene bromide (3 g.) added to it dropwise. After continuing the stirring for half an hour more at ordinary temperature, the contents were put into water (100 ml.) and extracted with chloroform. Removal of the solvent from the dried (Na_2SO_4) extract, yielded the alkylated β -ketosulphoxide (4.5 g.). This was dissolved in 10 per cent aqueous T.H.F. (270 ml.) and small pieces of freshly prepared aluminium amalgam (4 g. Al.) added to the stirred solution which was heated at 65° for 90 mins, thereafter. The reaction mixture was then filtered and residual solid washed well with T.H.F. The filtrate from which most of the T.H.F. had been removed by heating on a water bath was extracted with ether. The ether extract was washed with water, dried (Na_2SO_4) and the solvent evaporated. The residual oil was chromatographed over alumina using benzene-petroleum ether, $40-60^\circ$, (1 : 4-mixture) as eluent and fractionated under vacuum to furnish the ketone (V); b.p. $170^\circ/12$ mm., yield 2.4 g. (58.5%); η_D^{30} 1.4523. (Found : C, 71.63; H, 9.71. $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{24}\text{O}_3$ requires C, 71.39; H, 9.59%).

Infrared spectrum showed prominent peaks at 1700 cm^{-1} ($>\text{C}=\text{O}$) 1450 , 1380 cm^{-1} ($>\text{C}-\text{CH}_3$), 1040 cm^{-1} (ketal) and 835 , 785 cm^{-1} ($\text{R}_1\text{R}_2\text{C}=\text{CHR}_3$).

6-Methyl-2-(4,4-ethylenedioxy-cyclohexyl)1,5-heptadiene (VI): Methylene phosphorane was obtained from sodium hydride (0.24 g.) in dimethylsulphoxide (5 ml.) and methyltriphenylphosphonium iodide (4.05 g.) in dimethyl sulphoxide (10 ml.) under nitrogen atmosphere. To the phosphorane at room temperature was added the ketone (V, 2.3 g.) in dry T.H.F. (10 ml.). The contents were stirred, at 50° , for 3 hrs and left overnight at room temperature. The reaction mixture was then poured into cold water and extracted with petroleum ether ($40-60^\circ$). The combined extract was washed with water and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. Removal of the solvent, chromatography over alumina (eluent being petroleum ether, $40-60^\circ$) and vacuum distillation afforded (1.7 g.) 74% of the ketal (VI); b.p. $152-54^\circ/15$ mm., η_D^{30} 1.4567. (Found : C, 77.12; H, 10.64; $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{26}\text{O}_2$ requires C, 76.75; H, 10.47%).

I.R. spectrum showed characteristic bands at 1040 cm^{-1} (ketal), 3050 , 1650 , 890 cm^{-1} (methylene) and $830-35\text{ cm}^{-1}$ ($\text{R}_1\text{R}_2\text{C}=\text{CHR}_3$) and other peaks at 1455 , 1380 , 1320 , 1200 , 1105 , 945 , 922 , 785 cm^{-1} . There was no absorption in the carbonyl region.

6-Methyl-2-(4-oxo-cyclohexyl)-1,5-heptadiene (VII): The ketal (VI, 1.6 g.) was dissolved in acetone (20 ml.) and aqueous hydrochloric acid (10%, 5 ml.) and the reaction mixture was stirred for 2 hrs at room temperature. Thereafter, the contents were diluted with saturated sodium chloride solution (40 ml.) and extracted with ether. After drying (Na_2SO_4) and solvent removal, the residue was distilled to provide (0.96 g., 72%) of the ketone (VII); b.p. $148^\circ/15$ mm., η_D^{30} 1.4934. (Found : C, 81.95; H, 10.63. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}$ requires C, 81.50; H, 10.75%).

Infrared spectrum showed characteristic peaks at 1720 cm^{-1} ($>\text{C}=\text{O}$), 3050 , 1650 , 890 cm^{-1} (methylene), 835 cm^{-1} ($\text{R}_1\text{R}_2\text{C}=\text{CHR}_3$) and other bands at 1650 , 1455 , 1380 , 1320 , 1180 , 1120 and 960 cm^{-1} .

6-Methyl-2-(4-methylene-cyclohexyl)1,5-heptadiene (I): A solution of the ketone (VII, 0.8 g.) in dry tetrahydrofuran (5 ml.) was added to the freshly prepared methylene

triphenyl-phosphorane (obtained in the usual manner from sodium hydride (0.11 g.) in dimethyl sulphoxide (2.3 ml.) and methyltriphenylphosphoniumiodide (1.85 g.) dissolved in dimethyl sulphoxide (4.6 ml.) under nitrogen atmosphere. After stirring for 3 hrs at 50°, the contents were left overnight and worked up as usual. The product was purified over neutral alumina using petroleum ether (40–60°) eluent and subsequently distilled under reduced pressure to yield (0.55 g., 70%) of (I), b.p. 104–5°/8 mm., η_D^{30} 1.4963. (Found : C, 88.25; H, 11.87. Calcd. for $C_{15}H_{24}$: C, 88.16; H, 11.84).

1-Carboxy-4-methyl-3-cyclohexene (IX) : Grignard reagent prepared from magnesium (0.71 g.) and methyl iodide (4.5 g.) in dry ether (100 ml.) was added slowly with constant stirring to the well cooled keto-ester (II, 5 g.), dissolved in dry ether (50 ml.). After allowing to stand overnight, the reaction mixture was refluxed for 2 hrs, cooled in an ice-bath and decomposed with saturated solution of ammonium chloride. The contents were extracted with ether, the combined ether extract washed with sodium bisulphite solution and water and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. The residue (4.6 g.) left after the evaporation of the solvent was mixed with pyridine (32 ml.). The mixture was cooled to 0° and $POCl_3$ (4.8 ml.) added dropwise with stirring. After continuing the stirring for 2 hrs more at 0°, the contents were left overnight. The reaction mixture was added to ice, extracted with ether and worked up in the usual manner to furnish (3.12 g., 63%) of (IX); b.p. 90°/2–3 mm., η_D^{30} 1.4785. (Found : C, 71.87; H, 9.65. $C_{10}H_{16}O_2$ requires C, 71.39; H, 9.59%).

1-(1-Oxo-2-methylsulphinylethyl)-4-methyl-3-cyclohexene (X) : The above β -ketosulphoxide (X) was obtained as a semi-solid (2.6 g., 70%) from sodium hydride (0.86 g.), dimethyl sulphoxide (17.8 ml.) and the ester (IX, 3 g.) by adopting the same procedure as described under (IV). It was employed as such for the next reaction.

5-Methyl-1-(4-methyl-3-cyclohexenyl)-4-hexene-1-one (XI) : The β -ketosulphoxide (XI, 2.6 g.) in dry D.M.F. (12 ml.) was alkylated with isoprene bromide (2.0 g.) using sodium hydride (0.312 g.) in dry D.M.F. (36 ml.) in the manner described under (V). The resulting alkylated β -ketosulphoxide (2.8 g.) was dissolved in 10 per cent aqueous T.H.F. (170 ml.) and treated with aluminium amalgam prepared freshly from aluminium (3 g.). The residue obtained after the usual working up and removal of the solvent upon chromatography through alumina (eluent being 1 : 4 benzenepetroleum ether 40–60°, mixture) and distillation under reduced pressure afforded (1.56 g., 58%) of the ketone (XI), b.p. 126–29°/2–3 mm., η_D^{30} 1.4989. (Found : C, 81.63; H, 10.64. $C_{14}H_{22}O$ requires C, 81.50; H, 10.75%).

Infrared spectrum of the ketone showed characteristic peaks at 1720 cm^{-1} ($>C=O$) 830, 790 cm^{-1} ($R_1R_2C=CHR_3$).

6-Methyl-2-(4-methyl-3-cyclohexenyl)-1,5-heptadiene (VIII) : Methylene phosphorane was prepared in the usual manner from sodium hydride (0.192 g.) in dimethyl sulphoxide (4 ml.) and methyltriphenylphosphoniumiodide (3.3 g.) in dimethyl sulphoxide (8 ml.). After the addition of ketone (XI, 1.4 g.), the contents were stirred for 3 hrs at 50° and left overnight. The usual working up furnished a residue which was chromatographed over alumina using petroleum ether (40–60°) eluent. The product obtained was further purified

by vacuum distillation to obtain 0.95 g. (68%) of the hydrocarbon (II); b.p. 102–104°/3 mm., η_D^{30} 1.4868 (Lit.⁹ reports η_D^{20} 1.4880). (Found : C, 88.34; H, 11.72. $C_{15}H_{24}$ requires C, 88.16; H, 11.84%).

I.R. spectrum of the synthetic compound showed peaks at 2875, 1650, 1450, 1385, 1150, 1020, 910, 890, 830 and 795 cm^{-1} which are comparable to those reported for the natural as well as the earlier synthesised samples^{10–14}.

4-Acetyl-1,1-ethylenedioxy-cyclohexane (XIII) : 1-(1-oxo-2-methylsulphinyloxyethyl)-4,4-ethylenedioxy-cyclohexane (IV, 3 g.) was dissolved in 10 per cent aqueous T.H.F. (180 ml.) and treated with freshly prepared aluminium amalgam (3.5 g. aluminium) and worked up as already described under (V). The residue left after the solvent removal was chromatographed over alumina (1 : 4-benzene petroleum ether mixture employed as eluent) afforded (1.63 g., 72%) of the ketal-ketone (XIII); b.p. 120–25°/14 mm., η_D^{30} 1.4928 (Lit.²⁰ reports b.p. 120–27°/10 mm., and η_D^{22} 1.4951). (Found : C, 65.03; H, 8.82. $C_{10}H_{16}O_3$ requires C, 65.19; H, 8.75%).

I.R. spectrum showed characteristic peaks at 1720 cm^{-1} ($> C = O$), 1045, 1100, 1130 cm^{-1} (ketal) and 1460, 1375 cm^{-1} ($C-CH_3$).

4-Isopropenyl-cyclohexanone (XV) : The ketal-ketone (XIII) was transformed into the ketone (XV) by submitting it to Wittig reaction and deketalising the resulting product (XIV) according to the procedure described in literature²⁰.

I.R. spectrum of the ketone showed bands at 3055, 2950, 1720, 1440, 1370, 1230 and 890 cm^{-1} .

The ketone formed a yellow D.N.P., m.p. 129–30° (from ethanol). (Literature reports m.p. 120–21°,¹⁹ 129–30°²⁰). (Found : N, 17.92; $C_{15}H_{18}N_4O_4$ requires N, 17.61%).

1-Methyl-4-isopropenyl-cyclohexane-1-ol (XII) : Grignard reagent was prepared from dry magnesium turnings (150 mg.), methyl iodide (1 g.) and dry ether (30 ml.). It was well cooled and the ketone (XV, 0.5 g.) in dry ether (10 ml.) was added dropwise with constant stirring. The reaction mixture was left overnight at room temperature and then refluxed for 2 hrs to complete the reaction. Thereafter, the contents were cooled and decomposed with saturated solution of ammonium chloride and the aqueous phase thoroughly extracted with ether. The ether extract was dried (Na_2SO_4) and evaporated to remove the solvent. The residue was distilled under reduced pressure to obtain β -terpineol (XII); b.p. 100°/7mm., yield 0.4 g. (70%). On chilling, it crystallised into a solid, m.p. 31–32° (reported m.p. 32–33°). (Found : C, 77.72; H, 11.59. $C_{10}H_{18}O$ requires C, 77.86; H, 11.76%).

I.R. spectrum showed peaks at 3460, 3130, 2980, 1650, 1450, 1360, 1250, 1192, 1136, 1095, 1042, 955 and 890 cm^{-1} which are comparable to those given in literature^{18,19}.

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